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Modelling an Improved NOL Ring Test Using a Reduced Volume Method for The Characterisation of Composite Cylinders

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Composite Pressure Vessels (CPV)

- CPV is made from filament winding process
- Consists of different winding orientation (Hoop and Helical)
- Burst test (Acc. To ISO 11119-2:2012, at least 3 x nominal working pressure, with 1 MPa/s)
- Under internal pressure, the hoop layer behaves like a unidirectional composite under tension

NOL Ring test

© ASTM 2290

© BAM

ORIGINAL NOL

IMPROVED NOL

Alleviates gripping and specimens manufacturing issues

Multiscale fibre break model

Representative Volume Element

3D Finite Element

Macroscopic Structure

5 types i-plets break
 3DFE contain 8 RVE
 Each 3DFE requires 40 Fibre Strength Values

Reduced Volume Method

- Reduction of degree of freedoms (3993 to 1452)
- Less demanding computation
- Without compromising the failure prediction

Comparison with experiment

Cases	Fibre Vf (%)	Sectional Area (mm ²)
● 1	35	30
● 2		40
Cases	Fibre Vf (%)	Sectional Area (mm ²)
● 3	55	30
● 4		40

Comparison with experiment

- Case 3 predicted the failure within the scatter of experiment
- The reduced volume method has been favourably validated
- The time dependent effect can be seen with the model

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